

Mueller matrix as a commutative product of left- and right-isoclinic transformations in 4D complex space

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Abstract

In polarization optics, deterministic optical medium is characterized by the Jones matrix. \mathbf{Z} matrix is the 4×4 analogue of the Jones matrix and the corresponding Mueller matrix can be written as $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^*$. Jones matrix acts on the two component complex Jones vectors, while the \mathbf{Z} matrix acts on the four component real Stokes vectors. In this note it is shown that \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices can be interpreted as left- and right-isoclinic transformations in 4D complex space, which may correspond to Euclidean rotations or pseudo-Euclidean rotations or projections depending on the type of the Mueller matrix.

1 Introduction

In 4D real space, in a particularly chosen reference frame, an arbitrary 4D rotation matrix can be written as:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\delta_1) & -\sin(\delta_1) & 0 & 0 \\ \sin(\delta_1) & \cos(\delta_1) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos(\delta_2) & -\sin(\delta_2) \\ 0 & 0 & \sin(\delta_2) & \cos(\delta_2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

This is an orthogonal matrix with determinant +1. It defines a 4D rotation in two mutually orthogonal invariant planes of rotation, such that points in each plane stay within that plane, and there are two angles of rotation, δ_1 and δ_2 , for each plane [1–5].

If $\delta_1 = \pm\delta_2$, the rotation is called an isoclinic rotation. An isoclinic rotation can be left- or right-isoclinic depending on whether $\delta_1 = \delta_2$ or $\delta_1 = -\delta_2$, respectively. Thomas defines matrices corresponding to general left- and right-isoclinic rotations in 4D real space [1]:

$$\mathbf{R}_L = \begin{pmatrix} l_0 & -l_3 & l_2 & -l_1 \\ l_3 & l_0 & -l_1 & -l_2 \\ -l_2 & l_1 & l_0 & -l_3 \\ l_1 & l_2 & l_3 & l_0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{R}_R = \begin{pmatrix} r_0 & -r_3 & r_2 & r_1 \\ r_3 & r_0 & -r_1 & r_2 \\ -r_2 & r_1 & r_0 & r_3 \\ -r_1 & -r_2 & -r_3 & r_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Thus, any 4D rotation matrix in real space can be written as a commutative product known as Cayley's factorization [6–8]

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_L \mathbf{R}_R = \mathbf{R}_R \mathbf{R}_L \quad (3)$$

Thomas writes \mathbf{R}_L as a linear combination of basis matrices

$$\mathbf{R}_L = l_0\mathbb{1} + l_1\mathbf{A}_1 + l_2\mathbf{A}_2 + l_3\mathbf{A}_3, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is the 4×4 identity and

$$\mathbf{A}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A}_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

\mathbf{A}_i matrices obey the same algebra with the unit quaternions [9]

$$\mathbf{A}_1^2 = \mathbf{A}_2^2 = \mathbf{A}_3^2 = \mathbf{A}_1\mathbf{A}_2\mathbf{A}_3 = -\mathbb{1} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_1\mathbf{A}_2 = \mathbf{A}_3, \quad \mathbf{A}_2\mathbf{A}_3 = \mathbf{A}_1, \quad \mathbf{A}_3\mathbf{A}_1 = \mathbf{A}_2 \quad (7)$$

Similarly, the right-isoclinic rotation matrix, \mathbf{R}_R , can be written in terms of dual basis, \mathbf{B}_i

$$\mathbf{R}_R = l_0\mathbb{1} + r_1\mathbf{B}_1 + r_2\mathbf{B}_2 + r_3\mathbf{B}_3, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{B}_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

\mathbf{B}_i matrices obey the same algebra, and any \mathbf{A}_i commutes with any \mathbf{B}_j

$$\mathbf{A}_i\mathbf{B}_j = \mathbf{B}_j\mathbf{A}_i \quad (10)$$

We can make the first connection with the Mueller matrices by letting $l_0 = r_0 = \cos(\delta)$, $l_1 = r_1 = \sin(\delta)$ and $l_3 = r_3 = l_2 = r_2 = 0$

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \delta & 0 & 0 & -\sin \delta \\ 0 & \cos \delta & -\sin \delta & 0 \\ 0 & \sin \delta & \cos \delta & 0 \\ \sin \delta & 0 & 0 & \cos \delta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \delta & 0 & 0 & \sin \delta \\ 0 & \cos \delta & -\sin \delta & 0 \\ 0 & \sin \delta & \cos \delta & 0 \\ -\sin \delta & 0 & 0 & \cos \delta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(2\delta) & -\sin(2\delta) & 0 \\ 0 & \sin(2\delta) & \cos(2\delta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

This is the well known Mueller matrix of polarization optics for rotation of the coordinate system through an angle δ , or an ideal circular retarder that rotates the polarization state of light. Similarly, quarter-wave plates, half-wave plates and, in general, all retarders (unitary matrices) can be written as a commutative multiplication of left- and right-isoclinic transformations (rotations) in 4D real space [3].

But, it is not the case for diattenuator Mueller matrices (Hermitian matrices). They cannot be written as a multiplication of left- and right-isoclinic transformations in 4D real space. In this note it will shown that any Mueller matrix of nondepolarizing optical medium can be written as a commutative product of left- and right-isoclinic matrices in 4D complex space.

2 \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices and their dual bases for isoclinic transformations

If the medium is deterministic (nondepolarizing) its optical properties can be represented by a Jones matrix, or alternatively, by a vector state $|h\rangle$ or by a matrix state \mathbf{Z} [10–13]. Components of the vector state can be parametrized as:

$$|h\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{pmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where τ , α , β and γ are, in general, complex numbers. If the overall phase is not taken into account τ can be chosen to be real and positive. It was shown that α , β and γ are associated with complex anisotropy parameters of the optical system (details can be found in the Appendix).

$|h\rangle$ vector is the generator of the nondepolarizing Mueller matrix, and \mathbf{Z} is the matrix form of $|h\rangle$:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ \alpha & \tau & -i\gamma & i\beta \\ \beta & i\gamma & \tau & -i\alpha \\ \gamma & -i\beta & i\alpha & \tau \end{pmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Mueller matrix of a deterministic optical system can be written as a commutative multiplication of \mathbf{Z} by its complex conjugate:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z}. \quad (14)$$

Proof is given in the appendix. This is also a special form the factorization of the Lorentz matrix [14–16].

\mathbf{Z} matrix can be written in a compact form in terms of three basis matrices \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{J} , \mathbf{K} and 4×4 identity:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \tau\mathbb{1} + i\alpha\mathbf{I} + i\beta\mathbf{J} + i\gamma\mathbf{K} \quad (15)$$

where

$$\mathbb{1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{I} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

\mathbf{I} , \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{K} matrices obey the same algebra with the unit quaternions

$$\mathbf{I}^2 = \mathbf{J}^2 = \mathbf{K}^2 = \mathbf{IJK} = -\mathbb{1} \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{IJ} = \mathbf{K}, \quad \mathbf{JK} = \mathbf{I}, \quad \mathbf{KI} = \mathbf{J} \quad (18)$$

On the other hand, \mathbf{Z}^* matrix is based on different kind of matrices

$$\mathbf{Z}^* = \tau^* \mathbf{1} - i\alpha^* \mathbf{I}^* - i\beta^* \mathbf{J}^* - i\gamma^* \mathbf{K}^* \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{I}^* , \mathbf{J}^* and \mathbf{K}^* are the dual basis. They commute with \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{K} basis and they obey the same algebra, but they are of different kind. In fact, \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices are quaternions in matrix form, but they are not of the same kind. If we call the \mathbf{Z} matrix as a quaternion of the first kind then \mathbf{Z}^* is of the second kind, and the product $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{M}$ is not a quaternion of any kind: it is the real Mueller matrix of polarization optics:

$$\mathbf{M} = -\tau\tau^* \mathbf{1} + \alpha\alpha^* \mathbf{I}\mathbf{I}^* + \beta\beta^* \mathbf{J}\mathbf{J}^* + \gamma\gamma^* \mathbf{K}\mathbf{K}^* + 2\Re(\tau^* \mathbf{Z} + \alpha\beta^* \mathbf{I}\mathbf{J}^* + \alpha\gamma^* \mathbf{I}\mathbf{K}^* + \beta\gamma^* \mathbf{J}\mathbf{K}^*) \quad (20)$$

Multiplication table of $\mathbf{1}$, \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{J} , \mathbf{K} with their complex complex conjugates generate 16 basis matrices for the 4×4 matrix space, but the nondepolarizing Mueller matrix is not any matrix that can be expanded in these basis, it is the commutative product of \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices, which can be interpreted as left- and right-isoclinic transformations in 4D complex space.

3 Mueller matrix as a commutative product of isoclinic transformations

\mathbf{R}_L and \mathbf{R}_R matrices given in Eq.2 are both orthogonal matrices, therefore they can be directly associated with rotations in 4D real space. However, they are not suitable for expressing Mueller matrices as isoclinic transformations, in general. In this section it is shown that it is possible to write any nondepolarizing Mueller matrix as a commutative product of \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices which can be interpreted as left- and right-isoclinic transformations in 4D complex space.

3.1 Retarders and rotations on the Poincare sphere

In general, \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices cannot be directly interpreted as rotation matrices. But, if α , β and γ are pure imaginary numbers then \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices are unitary

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^\dagger = \mathbf{Z}^*(\mathbf{Z}^*)^\dagger = \mathbf{1} \quad (21)$$

where \dagger stands for Hermitian conjugate (conjugate, transpose) and we assume that $|h\rangle$ is normalized to unity. In this case $|h\rangle$ represents a general retarder and the corresponding \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices can be interpreted as left- and right-isoclinic rotation matrices. In particular, if $\tau = \cos \delta$, $\alpha = -in_x \sin \delta$, $\beta = -in_y \sin \delta$ and $\gamma = -in_z \sin \delta$, the associated Mueller matrix represents an ideal retarder that corresponds to the rotations of the polarization state of light (Stokes vector) on the Poincare sphere through an angle 2δ about an axis $\hat{n} = (n_x, n_y, n_z)^T$:

$$|h\rangle_R = \begin{pmatrix} C(\delta) \\ -in_x S(\delta) \\ -in_y S(\delta) \\ -in_z S(\delta) \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_R = \begin{pmatrix} C(\delta) & -in_x S(\delta) & -in_y S(\delta) & -in_z S(\delta) \\ -in_x S(\delta) & C(\delta) & -n_z S(\delta) & n_y S(\delta) \\ -in_y S(\delta) & n_z S(\delta) & C(\delta) & -n_x S(\delta) \\ -in_z S(\delta) & -n_y S(\delta) & n_x S(\delta) & C(\delta) \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \mathbf{M}_R = \mathbf{Z}_R \mathbf{Z}_R^* = \mathbf{Z}_R^* \mathbf{Z}_R \quad (22)$$

where $C(\delta) = \cos \delta$, $S(\delta) = \sin \delta$, $n_x = \cos(2\theta) \cos(2\phi)$, $n_y = \sin(2\theta) \cos(2\phi)$, $n_z = \sin(2\phi)$, 2θ and 2ϕ are the polar coordinates on the Poincare sphere.

In Eq.22 \mathbf{Z}_R and \mathbf{Z}_R^* matrices generate left- and right-isoclinic rotations and \mathbf{M}_R is equivalent to the famous Rodrigues formula for 3D rotations in the real space:

$$\mathbf{M}_R = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 - 2n_y^2 S^2 - 2n_z^2 S^2 & 2n_x n_y S^2 - 2n_z C S & 2n_x n_z S^2 + 2n_y C S \\ 0 & 2n_x n_y S^2 + 2n_z C S & 1 - 2n_x^2 S^2 - 2n_z^2 S^2 & 2n_y n_z S^2 - 2n_x C S \\ 0 & 2n_x n_z S^2 - 2n_y C S & 2n_y n_z S^2 + 2n_x C S & 1 - 2n_x^2 S^2 - 2n_y^2 S^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

In this example, it is not easy to define two invariant planes of rotation. We can get a simpler form of the Mueller matrix of an ideal linear retarder if we take $\gamma = 0$. We can do this by simply modifying Eq.23 by letting $\phi = 0$, $n_z = 0$ and $n_x = \cos(2\theta)$, $n_y = \sin(2\theta)$. In order to get a still more simpler representation we may rotate the coordinate system through an angle θ . After the rotation of the coordinate system new parameters reduces to $\tau = C(\delta)$, $\alpha = -iS(\delta)$, $\beta = 0$ and $\gamma = 0$ and the associated Mueller matrix $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^*$ reads as follows:

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} C(\delta) & -iS(\delta) & 0 & 0 \\ -iS(\delta) & C(\delta) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C(\delta) & -S(\delta) \\ 0 & 0 & S(\delta) & C(\delta) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} C(\delta) & iS(\delta) & 0 & 0 \\ iS(\delta) & C(\delta) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C(\delta) & -S(\delta) \\ 0 & 0 & S(\delta) & C(\delta) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C(2\delta) & -S(2\delta) \\ 0 & 0 & S(2\delta) & C(2\delta) \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

This is the Mueller matrix of an ideal linear retarder with a 0° fast axis.

Let us have a closer look at the basic feature of the isoclinic rotations in Eq.24. We observe that the upper and lower quadrants of the \mathbf{Z} matrix are 2×2 unitary matrices:

$$\mathbf{U}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} C(\delta) & -iS(\delta) \\ -iS(\delta) & C(\delta) \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{U}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} C(\delta) & -S(\delta) \\ S(\delta) & C(\delta) \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

\mathbf{U}_1 and \mathbf{U}_2 matrices are rotation matrices of $SU(2)$ that can be written in terms of Pauli matrices

$$\mathbf{U}_1 = C(\delta)\mathbb{1} - iS(\delta)\sigma_x, \quad \mathbf{U}_2 = C(\delta)\mathbb{1} - iS(\delta)\sigma_y \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is the 2×2 identity. Similarly, \mathbf{Z}^* consists of \mathbf{U}_1^* and \mathbf{U}_2^* matrices. \mathbf{U}_1 and \mathbf{U}_1^* rotate in opposite directions, $\mathbf{U}_1\mathbf{U}_1^* = \mathbb{1}$; but, \mathbf{U}_2 and \mathbf{U}_2^* rotate in the same direction, $\mathbf{U}_2\mathbf{U}_2^* = C(2\delta)\mathbb{1} - iS(2\delta)\sigma_y$. These are the characteristic properties of the left- and right-isoclinic rotations.

It is also possible to generate some other simple forms of unitary Mueller matrices. For example, if we let $\tau = C(\delta)$, $\alpha = 0$, $\beta = -iS(\delta)$ and $\gamma = 0$ we get a linear retarder, fast axis 45° , if we let $\tau = C(\delta)$, $\alpha = 0$, $\beta = 0$ and $\gamma = -iS(\delta)$ we get a circular retarder, fast axis 0° .

3.2 Diattenuators and projections on the Poincare sphere

If τ, α, β and γ are real, vector state $|h\rangle$ corresponds to a general diattenuator. As a simpler case let us consider a linear dichroism with $\tau = \cosh(\xi)$, $\alpha = -\sinh(\xi)$ and $\beta = \gamma = 0$ ($\xi = LD/2$):

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{M} &= \begin{pmatrix} Ch(\xi) & -Sh(\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ -Sh(\xi) & Ch(\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Ch(\xi) & iSh(\xi) \\ 0 & 0 & -iSh(\xi) & Ch(\xi) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Ch(\xi) & -Sh(\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ -Sh(\xi) & Ch(\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Ch(\xi) & -iSh(\xi) \\ 0 & 0 & iSh(\xi) & Ch(\xi) \end{pmatrix} \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} Ch(2\xi) & -Sh(2\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ -Sh(2\xi) & Ch(2\xi) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \tag{27}
\end{aligned}$$

where $Ch(\xi) = \cosh(\xi)$ and $Sh(\xi) = \sinh(\xi)$. The lower 2×2 quadrant of the Mueller matrix is an identity. The upper and lower quadrants of \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices now correspond to pseudo-Euclidean rotations [14].

Another example could be a linear polarizer defined by two attenuation coefficients $p_x = \cos(\psi) = C$ and $p_y = \sin(\psi) = S$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{M} &= \begin{pmatrix} C+S & C-S & 0 & 0 \\ C-S & C+S & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C+S & -i(C-S) \\ 0 & 0 & i(C-S) & C+S \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} C+S & C-S & 0 & 0 \\ C-S & C+S & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C+S & i(C-S) \\ 0 & 0 & -i(C-S) & C+S \end{pmatrix} \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & C(2\psi) & 0 & 0 \\ C(2\psi) & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & S(2\psi) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & S(2\psi) \end{pmatrix} \tag{28}
\end{aligned}$$

The lower and upper quadrants of \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* can be interpreted as pseudo-Euclidean rotations, and we can say that, the upper quadrants transform in the same way, but the lower quadrants transform in the opposite way. In fact, the lower quadrant of the Mueller matrix is a 2×2 identity scaled by a factor of $\chi = S(2\psi)$, and as $\chi \rightarrow 0$ \mathbf{M} evolves into an ideal polarizer.

If we let $\tau = 1$, $\alpha = \cos(2\theta) \cos(2\phi)$, $\beta = \sin(2\theta) \cos(2\phi)$ and $\gamma = \sin(2\phi)$ the corresponding \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices generate an ideal polarizer Mueller matrix that projects any input polarization state onto a polarization state defined by the angles 2θ and 2ϕ on the Poincare sphere, and the Mueller matrix becomes a projection operator

$$\mathbf{M} = |h\rangle\langle h|, \quad \mathbf{M}|s\rangle = \langle h|s\rangle|h\rangle. \tag{29}$$

As a simple example let us consider a linear horizontal polarizer with $\tau = 1/\sqrt{2}$, $\alpha = 1/\sqrt{2}$

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 1 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & i \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \tag{30}$$

In this simple example of an ideal polarizer the upper quadrants of \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices transform in the same way, but the lower quadrants cancel each other, in other words, $\chi = 0$ and \mathbf{M} reduces to an ideal projection operator.

4 Isoclinic transformation of the Stokes vector

In principle, \mathbf{Z} matrix is a 4×4 analogue of the Jones matrix, \mathbf{J} [13]:

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau + \alpha & \beta - i\gamma \\ \beta + i\gamma & \tau - \alpha \end{pmatrix}. \quad (31)$$

Jones matrix transforms two component Jones vectors, $|E\rangle$, into Jones vectors, $|E'\rangle$, and Mueller matrix transforms four component Stokes vectors, $|s\rangle$, into Stokes vectors, $|s'\rangle$:

$$|E'\rangle = \mathbf{J}|E\rangle, \quad (32)$$

$$|s'\rangle = \mathbf{M}|s\rangle, \quad (33)$$

where $|s\rangle = (s_0, s_1, s_2, s_3)^T$, $|s'\rangle = (s'_0, s'_1, s'_2, s'_3)^T$ (s_i and s'_i are real numbers). Mueller matrix of nondepolarizing (deterministic) optical medium transforms the Stokes vector of completely polarized light into another complete polarization state.

On the other hand, \mathbf{Z} matrix transforms the Stokes vector of completely polarized light, $|s\rangle$, into $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector:

$$|\tilde{s}\rangle = \mathbf{Z}|s\rangle, \quad (34)$$

where $|\tilde{s}\rangle = (\tilde{s}_0, \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \tilde{s}_3)^T$ and $\tilde{s}_0, \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2$ and \tilde{s}_3 are, in general, complex numbers. Hence \mathbf{Z} matrix transforms a real Stokes vector into a complex vector $|\tilde{s}\rangle$. But, \mathbf{Z}^* matrix brings $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ back onto the Poincare sphere

$$\mathbf{Z}^*|\tilde{s}\rangle = |s'\rangle \quad (35)$$

Appendix

It was shown that α , β and γ are the complex anisotropy parameters of the optical system [11]. In terms of spectroscopic parameters, isotropic phase retardation (η), isotropic amplitude absorption (κ), circular dichroism (CD), circular birefringence (CB), horizontal and 45° linear dichroism (LD and LD'), horizontal and 45° linear birefringence (LB and LB'), τ , α , β and γ can be written as:

$$\tau = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \alpha = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (36)$$

$$\beta = -e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iL'}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad \gamma = e^{-\frac{i\chi}{2}} \frac{iC}{T} \sin\left(\frac{T}{2}\right) \quad (37)$$

where $\chi = \eta - i\kappa$, $L = LB - iLD$, $L' = LB' - iLD'$, $C = CB - iCD$, $T = \sqrt{L^2 + L'^2 + C^2}$. Mueller matrix of a deterministic optical system can be written as

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z}. \quad (38)$$

It is easy to prove Eq.38 by recalling the well known relation

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{J} \otimes \mathbf{J}^*)\mathbf{A}^\dagger \quad (39)$$

where \mathbf{A} is defined as

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i & -i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (40)$$

We write the Eq.39 in a slightly different form

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{A}((\mathbf{J} \otimes \mathbf{I})\mathbf{A}^\dagger \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{J}^*))\mathbf{A}^\dagger, \quad (41)$$

and we define the \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Z}^* matrices as follows:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{J} \otimes \mathbf{I})\mathbf{A}^\dagger, \quad \mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{I} \otimes \mathbf{J}^*)\mathbf{A}^\dagger \quad (42)$$

Let us write \mathbf{Z} in a quaternion form, $\mathbf{Z} = \tau\mathbb{1} + i\alpha\mathbf{I} + i\beta\mathbf{J} + i\gamma\mathbf{K}$. $\det(\mathbf{Z}) = \tau^2 - \alpha^2 - \beta^2 - \gamma^2$. If $\det(\mathbf{Z}) = 1$ then $\mathbf{Z}^{-1} = \tau\mathbb{1} - i\alpha\mathbf{I} - i\beta\mathbf{J} - i\gamma\mathbf{K}$ is the inverse of \mathbf{Z} . Now, it is straightforward to calculate the inverse of the corresponding Mueller matrix

$$\mathbf{M}^{-1} = \mathbf{Z}^{-1}(\mathbf{Z}^{-1})^* \quad (43)$$

If τ, α, β and γ are real numbers, then \mathbf{Z} is Hermitian ($\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{Z}^\dagger$) and the corresponding Mueller matrix represents a general diattenuator. As a special case, if $\tau = 1$, $\alpha = \cos 2\theta \cos 2\phi$, $\beta = \sin 2\theta \cos 2\phi$ and $\gamma = \sin 2\phi$, $|h\rangle$ generates an ideal polarizer Mueller matrix that projects any input polarization state onto a polarization state on the Poincare sphere defined by the angles 2θ and 2ϕ :

$$|h\rangle_P = \begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \cos 2\theta \cos 2\phi \\ \sin 2\theta \cos 2\phi \\ \sin 2\phi \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_P \rightarrow \mathbf{M}_P = \mathbf{Z}_P \mathbf{Z}_P^* \quad (44)$$

The Mueller that is generated by $|h\rangle_P$ can be written as an outer product of $|h\rangle_P$ with itself

$$\mathbf{M}_P = |h\rangle_P \langle h|_P \quad (45)$$

By using this property it can be easily shown that \mathbf{M}_P is a projection operator:

$$\mathbf{M}_P |s\rangle = \langle h|_P |s\rangle |h\rangle_P \quad (46)$$

$|h\rangle_P$ corresponds to the Hermitian \mathbf{Z}_P matrix:

$$\mathbf{Z}_P = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \cos 2\theta \cos 2\phi & \sin 2\theta \cos 2\phi & \sin 2\phi \\ \cos 2\theta \cos 2\phi & 1 & -i \sin 2\phi & i \sin 2\theta \cos 2\phi \\ \sin 2\theta \cos 2\phi & i \sin 2\phi & 1 & -i \cos 2\theta \cos 2\phi \\ \sin 2\phi & -i \sin 2\theta \cos 2\phi & i \cos 2\theta \cos 2\phi & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (47)$$

Then, the corresponding Mueller matrix is

$$\mathbf{M}_P = \mathbf{Z}_P \mathbf{Z}_P^* \quad (48)$$

If τ is real, α, β, γ are pure imaginary numbers, then \mathbf{Z} is unitary ($\mathbf{Z}^{-1} = \mathbf{Z}^\dagger$) and the corresponding Mueller matrix represents a general retarder. If the \mathbf{Z} matrix is normalized to unity, i.e., if $\tau^2 + \alpha\alpha^* + \beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^* = 1$, then $\det(\mathbf{Z}) = 1$ and $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^\dagger = \mathbf{1}$. In particular, if $\tau = \cos \delta$, $\alpha = -in_x \sin \delta$, $\beta = -in_y \sin \delta$ and $\gamma = -in_z \sin \delta$ the associated Mueller matrix, \mathbf{M}_R , is an ideal retarder that rotates the input Stokes vector ccw on the Poincare sphere through an angle 2δ about an axis $\hat{n} = (n_x, n_y, n_z)^T$:

$$|h\rangle_R = \begin{pmatrix} C \\ -in_x S \\ -in_y S \\ -in_z S \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \mathbf{Z}_R = \begin{pmatrix} C & -in_x S & -in_y S & -in_z S \\ -in_x S & C & -n_z S & n_y S \\ -in_y S & n_z S & C & -n_x S \\ -in_z S & -n_y S & n_x S & C \end{pmatrix}, \rightarrow \mathbf{M}_R = \mathbf{Z}_R \mathbf{Z}_R^* = \mathbf{Z}_R^* \mathbf{Z}_R \quad (49)$$

where $C = \cos \delta$, $S = \sin \delta$.

Another way of transforming the Stokes vector is a quaternion rotation given in [13]. Here we write it in its matrix form:

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{Z}^\dagger = \mathbf{S}' \quad (50)$$

where \dagger is for Hermitian conjugate and $\mathbf{Z}^\dagger = 1\tau^* - i\alpha^*\mathbf{I}^\dagger - i\beta^*\mathbf{J}^\dagger - i\gamma^*\mathbf{K}^\dagger = 1\tau^* + i\alpha^*\mathbf{I} + i\beta^*\mathbf{J} + i\gamma^*\mathbf{K}$, hence \mathbf{Z}^\dagger corresponds to a quaternion of the first kind, and \mathbf{S} is the matrix form of the Stokes quaternion:

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{pmatrix} s_0 & s_1 & s_2 & s_3 \\ s_1 & s_0 & -is_3 & is_2 \\ s_2 & is_3 & s_0 & -is_1 \\ s_3 & -is_2 & is_1 & s_0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (51)$$

The Eq.50 is equivalent to Eq.33 and both equations transform real Stokes vectors into real Stokes vectors without introducing any phase difference between input and output vectors. However, this is not true, in general, light acquires an overall phase as it passes through the optical medium and this phase is encoded in the overall phase of the output Jones vector, $|E'\rangle$. It can be shown that, just like the Jones matrix, the \mathbf{Z} matrix and hence the $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector bears the total phase introduced by the optical system [13]:

$$\langle E|E'\rangle = \langle E|\mathbf{J}|E\rangle = \frac{1}{2}\langle s|\mathbf{Z}|s\rangle = \frac{1}{2}\langle s|\tilde{s}\rangle. \quad (52)$$

Therefore, \mathbf{Z} matrices transform the Stokes vector of complete polarization, $|s\rangle$, into a complex vector $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ which bears the phase introduced by the optical element. This can be verified by showing that cyclic operations on the Poincare sphere with \mathbf{Z} matrices gives the Pancharatnam-Berry geometric phase which is accumulated in the \tilde{s}_0 element of the resultant $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector.

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